

Investigating the anomalous layer along the lunar core-mantle boundary by simultaneous elastic-wave velocity and density measurements. A. Néri¹, J. Chantel¹, L. Henry², A. Fienga³ and C. Ganino³, ¹UMET – Unité Matériaux et Transformations, Université de Lille, Lille, France, ²Synchrotron SOLEIL, Gif-sur-Yvette, France, ³GéoAzur, Université de la Côte d’Azur, Observatoire de la Côte d’Azur, Valbonne, France.

Introduction: The Moon is thought to have formed from a giant impact. Following this cataclysmic event, some planetary materials were ejected into orbit around the Earth and re-accreted to form the Moon [1]. Due to the massive amount of energy released during this giant impact, a lunar magma ocean developed. Its subsequent cooling and bottom-up crystallization are the most likely driving processes that layered the satellite into a crust, a mantle and a core [2]. However, lunar seismic data highlight an anomalous Low-Velocity Zone (LVZ) along the core-mantle boundary (CMB) [3]. Tidal deformation models of the Moon suggest that the LVZ is best explained by a larger density and lower viscosity than the mantle [4]. Experimentally determined fractional crystallization trends for lunar compositions indicate that the residual melt becomes progressively enriched in FeO and TiO₂ until ilmenite crystallizes [e.g. 5]. Due to its large density ($\approx 4800 \text{ kg.m}^{-3}$) compared to silicates ($\approx 3300 \text{ kg.m}^{-3}$), the accumulation of dense ilmenite at the top of the lunar mantle causes gravitational instabilities, driving the overturn of the lunar mantle [6]. The subsequent sinking of ilmenite-bearing cumulates to the CMB would increase density and most likely form the LVZ. However, the nature of the LVZ is still controversial. Two main hypotheses prevail: (1) the LVZ is formed by the accumulation of solid and dense ilmenite, or (2) the LVZ is formed by the accumulation of a dense partial melt that remains neutrally buoyant. Both hypotheses have their own strengths and weaknesses, but ultimately, only the addition of new experimental data will help in discriminating between these scenarios. Thus, we conducted *in-situ* high-pressure and high-temperature experiments at the PSICHÉ beamline of the SOLEIL synchrotron (Paris, France) to investigate the nature of the LVZ.

Methods: In this work, the solid ilmenite accumulated along the CMB scenario is investigated. To do so, samples composed of a lunar model composition [7] were synthesized using an atmosphere-controlled furnace and were subsequently mixed with varying ilmenite proportions.

Ultrasonic measurements allow the simultaneous measurements of both P- and S-wave velocities through materials of interest [8]. In turn, the Beer-Lambert absorption method enables the measurement of density of complex samples [9], composed of multiple phases. Both techniques are thus well-suited to investigate the mechanical properties of our complex samples, with compositions representative of natural rocks. Hence, a technical development has

been conducted on PSICHÉ to enable its combination. A Paris-Edinburgh assembly was adapted to comply with the requirements of both techniques, and density and elastic-wave velocity data were successfully and quasi-simultaneously collected up to 5 GPa and 1600 K.

Results and conclusion: Thanks to these experiments, we could successfully determine the velocity-density relations of lunar mantle compositions with varying amounts of ilmenite. Our results show that the accumulation of ilmenite along the CMB is a process indeed able to increase the density of the LVZ. Comparing our data with seismic and tidal observations would require an ilmenite content of the LVZ that is realistic, based on lunar composition models. In turn, an accumulation of ilmenite is also able to decrease both the P- and S-wave velocities. However, the magnitude of this velocity reduction is far from matching the elastic wave velocities observed from seismic data.

Based on these results, we argue that the mechanical properties of the lunar LVZ cannot be explained by the sole accumulation of solid ilmenite. The amplitude of the P- and S-wave velocity reduction also requires the accumulation of a partial melt, similar to the basal molten layer observed on Mars [10,11].

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